

The nexus between utilitarian and hedonic motivations, online shopping satisfaction, and purchase intentions

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This study examines the nexus between utilitarian and hedonic motivations, online shopping satisfaction, and purchase intentions, focusing on the mediating role of online shopping satisfaction. Employing a descriptive research design and a single cross-sectional survey in South Africa, the results indicate that both utilitarian and hedonic motivations are significant predictors of online shopping satisfaction, which, in turn, influences purchase intentions. However, utilitarian motivations exhibit a stronger predictive power for online shopping satisfaction than hedonic ones. Further, online shopping satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between utilitarian motivations and purchase intentions; however, it partially mediates the relationship between hedonic motivations and purchase intentions. By balancing utilitarian and hedonic elements, business managers can cater to diverse motivational needs, fostering stronger customer relationships and increasing revenue potential.

Keywords: utilitarian, hedonic, satisfaction, intention, online shopping

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Introduction

Online shopping, or purchasing products through the Internet of Things (IoT), has become an integral part of our daily lives in many ways. While billions of people must still gain access to the Internet and be able to engage in activities such as online shopping, a significant number of people, including those in developing economies, have already done so. Figures from Statista (2024) indicate, "currently, there were 5.44b internet users worldwide, which amounted to 67 percent of the global population. Of this total, five billion, or 62 percent of the world's population, were social media users", offering an excellent opportunity for e-commerce. By the end of 2023, worldwide online shopping revenue was estimated at 6 trillion USD, projected to surpass eight trillion dollars by 2027. Smartphones accounted for almost 74 percent of retail site visits globally in the first quarter of 2023. They generated 63 percent of online shopping orders (Chevalier 2023), signifying the importance of mobile phone usage in consumers' daily activities.

COVID-19 has positively impacted the global adoption of online shopping and e-commerce. This is most likely one of the few positive impacts of the pandemic. During the first year of the COVID-19

outbreak, online consumer spending in South Africa increased by 68 percent (Newsroom 2020) and has been steadily growing. Beyond the points made above, there is a real business case for the phenomenal growth of the e-commerce industry. Businesses are drawn into online retailing and e-commerce because of the unique opportunity created by the Internet to reach a large and diverse consumer base, which results in reduced costs of maintaining *brick and mortar* stores and reduced labor costs. Similarly, consumers are drawn to online shopping due to its convenience.

As elucidated above, online shopping has become a popular and easy way to purchase products and services, and understanding what influences customer satisfaction and purchase intention in the online environment is therefore crucial. Briefly described, utilitarian motivation refers to the practical benefits of a product or service, such as price, quality, performance, convenience, dependability, or reliability (Babin & Harris 2016). In contrast, hedonic motivations are more emotional in nature, such as pleasure derived from using the product or service (Arnold & Reynolds 2003). Evidence in the literature suggests that utilitarian and hedonic motivations positively contribute to customer satisfaction (Anand et al. 2019), and customer satisfaction positively influences purchase intentions (Bai, Law & Wen 2008). This study, therefore, aims to investigate the nexus between utilitarian and hedonic motivations, online shopping satisfaction, and purchase intentions, with a particular focus on the mediating role of online shopping satisfaction. By doing so, the study aims to bridge the existing gap in the literature and provide valuable empirical insights, as no prior research has specifically addressed this issue. This research intends to fill the void by offering a comprehensive analysis and contributing to the academic discourse, which currently lacks a thorough exploration of the subject.

Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

Utilitarian Motivation

Utilitarian motivation refers to the "gratification derived from something that enables the consumer to solve problems or accomplish tasks" (Babin & Harris 2016). Utilitarian motivations are related to efficiency and logical decision-making processes; they pertain to an object's usefulness, functional value, worth, or qualities (Batra & Ahtola 1991). In other words, they are goal-oriented traits related to efficiency and logical decision-making; they pertain to an object's utility or functional value (Davis, Lang & Gautam 2013; Redda 2020). In the digital marketplace, utilitarian motivations manifest in various ways, such as the pursuit of time savings, cost-effectiveness, or the convenience of accessing products online (Fang et al. 2016). These motivations are often seen in consumers who prioritize product features, reliability, and overall value for money when purchasing. For instance, a consumer with utilitarian motivations might prefer online shopping for the ability to quickly compare prices, read reviews, or find specific items without the need for physical store visits (Davis et al. 2013)

Literature has shown that utilitarian motivations are crucial in shaping online shopping satisfaction and subsequent purchase intentions. For example, consumers with strong utilitarian motivations tend to focus on the efficiency and effectiveness of their shopping experience, which directly influences their satisfaction levels. This, in turn, enhances the likelihood of repeat purchases and positive purchase intentions (Lee & Wu 2017). Understanding the impact of utilitarian motivations on consumer behavior is essential for e-commerce platforms aiming to cater to consumers seeking practical and functional benefits in their online shopping experience.

Hedonic Motivation

Hedonic motivation refers to the drive to engage in activities primarily for the sake of experiencing pleasure, enjoyment, or emotional satisfaction (Batra & Ahtola 1991). In consumer behavior, hedonic motivation is the desire for sensory gratification, excitement, novelty, or fun that a person seeks from a product or service. Hedonic attributes include sensory experiences such as emotion, satisfaction, and

fantasy (Arnold & Reynolds 2003). As a result, emotional or sensory shopping experiences are the driving factors of hedonic consumption incentives (Redda 2020). In hedonic shopping, consumers emphasize the shopping process (To et al. 2007).

Hedonic motivation often leads consumers to prioritize the enjoyment of the shopping journey rather than acquiring specific products or services (Kim, Lee & Kim 2011). This drive for sensory pleasure and emotional engagement is evident in impulse buying, browsing for enjoyment, and exploring new or unique products (Ponsignon, Bauman & Lunardo 2024). Consumers motivated by hedonic factors may derive satisfaction from the aesthetics of a product, the joy of discovering new items, or the thrill of an unexpected find, emphasizing the experiential aspects of shopping (Haq, Khan & Ghouri 2014).

Research suggests that hedonic motivations significantly influence online shopping behavior, particularly in environments that offer rich, immersive experiences (Chang et al. 2023). For instance, online platforms that provide visually appealing interfaces, personalized content, and interactive features can enhance the hedonic value of shopping, fostering greater engagement and emotional satisfaction (Bilgihan, Kandampully & Zhang 2016). The emphasis on the sensory and emotional aspects of shopping underlines the importance of creating compelling digital environments that cater to hedonic consumers, who are driven not just by the end purchase but by the pleasurable experiences encountered along the way (Lee & Wu 2017). Understanding hedonic motivation is therefore essential for e-commerce platforms aiming to attract and retain consumers who value the experiential dimensions of shopping.

Online Shopping Satisfaction

When considering online shopping satisfaction, it is important to understand how utilitarian and hedonic values can contribute. Utilitarian value is important in satisfaction because it relates directly to practical concerns about the product or service being purchased (Anitha & Krishnan 2021). If customers feel that they are getting good value for their money—in terms of quality, price, and performance—they will be more satisfied with their purchase decisions (Davis et al. 2013). Hedonic motivation also contributes significantly to overall satisfaction with an online shopping experience (Evelina et al. 2020). This is because customers often derive pleasure from their purchases; they may be excited about acquiring something new or feel good about finding a bargain price on an item they want (Kertasunjaya, Mediasari & Manaf 2020). These emotional responses help create an overall enjoyable customer experience when shopping online.

Online Purchase Intention and Satisfaction as a Mediator

Online purchase intention refers to a consumer's conscious plan or willingness to buy a product or service through an online platform (Meskaran, Ismail & Shanmugam 2013). It represents the cognitive and affective components of a consumer's decision-making process, reflecting the likelihood that they will complete an online transaction (Chen, Lu & Wang 2017). Few studies have explored the mediating role of satisfaction, for example, between hedonic and utilitarian and e-loyalty (Doghan & Albarq 2022), between website quality and intention (Tandon, Kiran & Sah 2017), and between e-service quality and purchase intention (Lestari & Ellyawati 2019). However, the mediating role of online shopping satisfaction in the relationship between utilitarian and hedonic motivations and purchase intentions, consumer behavior within digital contexts is unexplored. Therefore, this study provides insights into how e-commerce platforms can optimize their strategies to enhance customer satisfaction and drive purchase intentions by focusing on utilitarian and hedonic motivational drivers. By examining the interplay between these factors, this study addresses a gap in the literature regarding their combined effect on online shopping behaviors and purchase intentions. Such understanding is crucial for e-commerce retailers seeking to improve customer engagement and conversion rates in highly competitive online markets.

Research Objectives

As elucidated above, utilitarian motivation is based on an action or decision's practical, functional, or instrumental value. Individuals motivated by utilitarian considerations focus on achieving practical benefits or solving problems. They prioritize efficiency, effectiveness, and the usefulness of their choices. In contrast, hedonic motivation is driven by the pursuit of pleasure, enjoyment, and sensory gratification. People with hedonic motivations seek experiences or products that offer immediate satisfaction, comfort, or indulgence. Utilitarian and hedonic motivations often intersect in consumer decision-making, with individuals evaluating practical benefits alongside personal enjoyment. Recognizing and understanding these motivations is essential for businesses and marketers, as it allows them to craft targeted marketing strategies, develop appealing products, and deliver services that resonate with a diverse consumer base. By addressing both the practical and emotional aspects of consumer needs and desires, businesses can create more compelling value propositions and enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. Accordingly, the following questions have been formulated to guide the study: (1) Do utilitarian and hedonic motivations influence customer satisfaction in an online shopping environment? (2) Do utilitarian and hedonic motivations directly influence online purchase intentions? (3) Does online shopping satisfaction directly influence online purchase intentions? (4) Does online shopping satisfaction play a mediating or intervening role between the two motivations (utilitarian and hedonic motivations) and online purchase intentions?

In line with the literature review and research questions, the study aims to examine the nexus between utilitarian and hedonic motivations, online shopping satisfaction, and purchase intentions, with a particular focus on the mediating role of online shopping satisfaction

Hypotheses Formulation

The section below elucidates the hypothesis formation in support of the research objective of the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: the author. Dotted lines = mediation.

Utilitarian Motivation on Online Shopping Satisfaction and Purchase Intentions

Utilitarian motivation can be described as goal-oriented behavior where customers seek efficiency, convenience, and functional benefits during their online shopping experience. Previous research suggests that when online platforms meet utilitarian needs, customers are likely to feel satisfied (Redda 2024). For

instance, consumers driven by strong utilitarian motivations prioritize the efficiency and effectiveness of their shopping experience, which directly impacts their satisfaction levels (Lee & Wu 2017). One can, therefore, argue that when online shopping experiences align more closely with consumers' utilitarian expectations, such as efficiency, reliability, and ease of use, customer satisfaction is likely to be significantly enhanced. Consumers driven by utilitarian motives seek a seamless, goal-oriented shopping process that minimizes effort and maximizes functionality. When online platforms effectively cater to such expectations by offering streamlined navigation, clear product descriptions, fast checkout processes, and dependable delivery services, shoppers are more likely to perceive the experience as valuable and satisfying (Khan et al. 2023). Accordingly, the study posits that:

H1. Utilitarian motivation positively impacts customer satisfaction.

Customers driven by utilitarian motives are more likely to prioritize functional and practical aspects of online platforms, such as ease of navigation, quick transactions, and reliable services (Febrilia, Rahmi, Lada & Chekima 2024). Such attributes are said to directly influence their purchasing decisions, independent of satisfaction (Fülöp et al. 2023). When consumers perceive online shopping as an effective means to fulfill their functional needs, they are more inclined to complete transactions, as the perceived benefits outweigh potential uncertainties. Factors such as ease of navigation, quick access to product information, secure payment methods, and reliable delivery services enhance the efficiency and practicality of online shopping, reinforcing consumers' confidence in the purchasing process (Islam 2024). Additionally, utilitarian shoppers prioritize the ability to compare prices, access discounts, and find specific products with minimal effort, further strengthening their purchase intentions (Chang et al. 2023). Since utilitarian motivation is rooted in goal-oriented and rational decision-making, consumers are more likely to complete transactions when e-commerce platforms meet their expectations for convenience and functionality. Consequently, utilitarian motivation acts as a critical driver of online purchase intentions by reducing decision-making complexity, increasing perceived value, and ensuring a seamless shopping experience (Magai 2024). Thus, it is postulated that:

H2. Utilitarian motivation positively influences online purchase intentions.

Hedonic Motivation – Customer Satisfaction and Online Purchase Intentions

Hedonic motivation enhances online shopping satisfaction by creating enjoyable, immersive, and emotionally engaging experiences. Hedonic motivation is associated with the enjoyment, pleasure, and emotional gratification derived from the shopping experience, directly influencing customer satisfaction (Magai 2024). Online platforms offering engaging content, aesthetic appeal, and interactive features often enhance customers' emotional satisfaction (Cai & Xu 2011). Redda (2024) found that "status, adventure, social shopping, idea shopping, and gratification," dimensions of hedonic motivation, significantly contribute to customer satisfaction. In line with this literature evidence, the third hypothesis is as follows:

H3. Hedonic motivation positively impacts customer satisfaction.

Hedonic motivation, driven by the pursuit of enjoyment, sensory stimulation, and emotional gratification, plays a crucial role in shaping online purchase intentions (Fülöp et al. 2023). Unlike utilitarian consumers, hedonic shoppers engage in online shopping for pleasure, entertainment, and experiential value rather than solely for functional benefits (Parker & Wang 2016). Research indicates that visually appealing websites, interactive features, and personalized recommendations enhance the enjoyment of online shopping, thereby increasing purchase likelihood (Koufaris 2002). Hedonic motivation encourages impulse buying, as emotionally driven shoppers are more likely to be influenced by persuasive triggers like flash

sales, exclusive deals, and visually appealing product displays (Platon 2024). One can argue that by creating an enjoyable and immersive shopping experience, e-commerce platforms can leverage hedonic motivation to strengthen consumer engagement and positively influence online purchase intentions. The study thus hypothesizes that:

H4. Hedonic motivation positively influences online purchase intentions.

Customer Satisfaction — Online Purchase Intentions

The concept of satisfaction, referring to consumers' fulfilment response (Oliver, Rust & Varki 1997), is viewed as a comparison between customer expectations and experience of the actual delivery of a product or a service (Bloemer & De Ruyter 2017), and it plays a pivotal role in any kind of business. Literature suggests that when consumers are content with their online shopping experiences, they are more likely to make repeat purchases and recommend the platform to others. For example, the study by Coker (2013) identifies four key dimensions, navigation, content, performance, and trust, that significantly influence website satisfaction and customer loyalty. Satisfied customers exhibit higher loyalty and engage in positive word-of-mouth, further enhancing the retailer's reputation and attracting new customers (Maxham 2001). Therefore, ensuring high levels of customer satisfaction is essential for fostering positive online purchase intentions and sustaining business growth (Coker 2013). In line with this narrative, this study posits that:

H5. Customer satisfaction positively influences online purchase intentions.

Customer Satisfaction as a Mediator

Customer satisfaction as a construct has been treated as a mediator in a variety of contexts, between website quality and purchase intentions (Tandon et al. 2017), between satisfaction and loyalty (Picón Castro & Roldán 2014), between e-satisfaction and online purchase intentions (Trivedi & Yadav 2018), and between E-banking quality and customer loyalty (Redda 2023). Other studies that attempted to explore the mediating role of satisfaction include Doghan and Albarq (2022), between hedonic and utilitarian and e-loyalty, Tandon, Kiran and Sah (2017), between website quality and intention, and Lestari and Ellyawati (2019), between e-service quality and purchase intention.

The present study aims to test the mediating role of customer satisfaction between the two motivations (utilitarian and hedonic motivations) and purchase intentions, which are currently not covered in empirical studies. Thus, this study argues that customer satisfaction is pivotal in mediating the relationship between utilitarian and hedonic motivations and online purchase intentions. For instance, when online retailers effectively cater to utilitarian motivations by offering user-friendly interfaces, efficient navigation, and reliable services, customers' functional needs are met, increasing satisfaction. This heightened satisfaction may subsequently enhance their intention to make purchases. Conversely, when retailers provide engaging, aesthetically pleasing, and enjoyable shopping experiences that appeal to hedonic motivations, customers derive pleasure from the process, which may result in greater satisfaction and a higher likelihood of purchasing. By addressing both utilitarian and hedonic aspects of their online businesses, retailers can effectively enhance customer satisfaction, positively influencing online purchase intentions. Based on the literature reviewed above and the argument put forward, this study postulates the following two hypotheses:

H6. Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between utilitarian motivation and online purchase intention.

H7. Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between hedonic motivation and online purchase intentions.

Methodology

A descriptive research design with a quantitative method was applied in this study. The study employed non-probability sampling strategies such as convenience and snowball sampling. A structured self-administered questionnaire was issued using *SurveyMonkey* to collect data from diverse internet buyers in Gauteng—South Africa’s economic hub. Using this data collection method, 215 valid responses were received and analyzed. The study conformed to ethical standards and obtained ethics clearance. This study's variables and measuring items for the utilitarian, hedonic, and satisfaction components were derived from previously validated instruments. A mediation analysis was performed using the PROCESS macro (Hayes 2018) to explore the mediating role of online shopping satisfaction in the relationship between hedonic and utilitarian motivations and online purchase intentions. Non-parametric bootstrapping was employed to test the indirect effect. The analysis utilized 50,000 bootstrap samples, with the percentile bootstrap estimation method and a 95% confidence interval (Shrout & Bolger 2002).

Analyses and Results

Table 1 reports the correlation coefficient between the four study constructs. The results indicate a significant positive association between each pair of the study constructs. The signs of the correlation were as expected and logically pointed toward the nomological validity of the measurement theory. Multicollinearity was not an issue as the coefficients are below .9 and VIF under 10. Similarly, Cronbach's Alphas (>.7) suggest the internal consistency and reliability of the scales.

Table 1. Correlation Analysis

	Utilitarian	Hedonic	Satisfaction	Intentions
Utilitarian	1			
Hedonic	.80**	1		
Satisfaction	.75**	.69**	1	
Intentions	.45**	.69**	.40**	1

** $p < .001$

Table 2 illustrates the results of the beta coefficients of the regression analysis (adjusted $R^2 = .59$). The two motivations (hedonic and utilitarian motivations), the independent variables (IVs), were regressed with customer satisfaction, the dependent variable (DV). H1, postulated as *utilitarian motivation positively impacts customer satisfaction*, is accepted ($\beta = .57$, $p < .00$). Similarly, H3, posited as *hedonic motivation positively impacts customer satisfaction*, is accepted ($\beta = .22$, $p < .00$). Regarding effect size, utilitarian motivations ($\beta = .57$) have a stronger predictor of customer satisfaction than hedonic motivations ($\beta = .33$). This finding corroborates the findings of Lee and Wu (2017), who found “the effect of utilitarian value on satisfaction to be greater than that of hedonic value.”

Table 2. Coefficients of Regression Analysis – DV: Customer Satisfaction

	Unstandardized	Standardized	p	VIF	Results
Constant	-.26		.46		
Utilitarian	.74	.57	.00	2.85	H1 → supported
Hedonic	.33	.22	.00	2.85	H3 → supported

H2, utilitarian motivation positively influences online purchase intentions, is supported ($\beta = .46$, $p < .00$). H6, customer satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between utilitarian motivation and online

purchase intentions ($\beta=.14, p>.05$). Customer satisfaction was also tested (Regression adjusted $R^2=.16$) as a predictor of purchase intentions. $H5$, customer satisfaction has a significant positive effect on online purchase intention, is not accepted ($\beta=.15, p>.05$). $H4$, hedonic motivation positively influences online purchase intentions, is supported ($\beta=.17, p<.05$). $H7$, customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between hedonic motivation and online purchase intention ($\beta=.14, p<.05$). However, since the direct effect of hedonic motivation on online purchase intention remained significant ($p<.01$) even after accounting for the mediation effect of satisfaction, this mediation is classified as partial mediation (Hayes 2018).

Table 3. Path Analysis Results

<i>Paths</i>	<i>Effects</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Results</i>
Utilitarian → Intention	.46	.00	$H2$: Supported
Satisfaction → Intention	.15	.12	$H5$: Not supported
Utilitarian → Satisfaction → Intention	.14	.11	$H6$: Not supported
Hedonic → Intention	.17	.00	$H4$: Supported
Hedonic → Satisfaction → Intention	.14	.00	$H7$: Supported

Discussion

We can draw several conclusions regarding the nexus between utilitarian motivations, hedonic motivations, online shopping satisfaction, and online purchase intentions. The analysis indicates no significant mediating role of online shopping satisfaction in the relationship between utilitarian motivations and online purchase intentions. This means that the influence of utilitarian motivations on online purchase intentions is not significantly channeled through online shopping satisfaction. However, the mediation analysis does show evidence of partial mediation between hedonic motivations and online purchase intentions through the online shopping satisfaction of consumers. This suggests that while hedonic motivations directly impact online purchase intentions, a portion of their influence is passed through customer satisfaction. In other words, online shopping satisfaction acts as a mediator, partially explaining the relationship between hedonic motivations and online purchase intentions. The findings of the present research add to the growing body of knowledge of prior studies that have explored the mediating role of satisfaction within other contexts, such as between hedonic and utilitarian and e-loyalty (Daghan & Albarq 2022), between website quality and intention (Tandon et al. 2017), and between e-service quality and purchase intention (Lestari & Ellyawati 2019).

Online shopping, facilitated by the Internet and the Internet of Things (IoT), has become an essential part of modern life, though many people worldwide still lack access. A substantial number, however, including those in developing economies, are already engaged in online shopping. Mobile devices play a crucial role in this growth, accounting for nearly 74 percent of retail site visits and 63 percent of online shopping orders in early 2023, highlighting the importance of smartphones in daily consumer behavior.

Given the importance of e-commerce in the global economy, this study contributes to the expanding body of research on online shopping behavior by offering deeper insights into how consumers make decisions in digital environments. The findings reveal that utilitarian and hedonic motivations significantly predict online shopping satisfaction, subsequently influencing online purchase intentions. Moreover, the study shows that utilitarian motivations exert a stronger effect on shopping satisfaction than hedonic motivations.

The mediation analysis part of the study indicates that online shopping satisfaction does not play a significant mediating role in the link between utilitarian motivations and online purchase intentions. This means that the level of online shopping satisfaction does not primarily influence the impact of utilitarian motivations on online purchase intentions. In contrast, the mediation analysis provides evidence of partial

mediation between hedonic motivations and online purchase intentions through online shopping satisfaction. This indicates that while hedonic motivations directly affect online purchase intentions, a portion of their influence is conveyed through the level of online shopping satisfaction experienced by consumers. In simpler terms, online shopping satisfaction acts as a mediator, partially explaining the connection between hedonic motivations and online purchase intentions.

Conclusion

This study's findings offer valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms that drive online purchase intentions, considering consumers' motivations and satisfaction within the context of online shopping. Recognizing the role of mediating variables, such as online shopping satisfaction, could benefit businesses and marketers, as it enables them to develop targeted strategies to enhance consumer satisfaction and optimize online purchase behavior. However, it is crucial to remember that the conclusions made from this study are specific to the data and context of this study. To ensure the generalizability and reliability of the results, further research and replication studies should be carried out in various contexts and with diverse samples.

This study provides valuable insights into the interplay between utilitarian and hedonic motivations, online shopping satisfaction, and purchase intentions. However, future research could explore the role of additional moderating variables, such as trust, perceived risk, and personal involvement, to gain deeper insight. Longitudinal studies could also provide a deeper understanding of how consumer motivations and satisfaction evolve over time. Expanding the study to different cultural and economic contexts could also enhance the generalizability of the findings.

Despite its contributions, the study has limitations, as any study does. Using a cross-sectional research design limits the ability to establish causality between the studied variables. The sample was drawn from South African online consumers, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other markets. Additionally, it must be noted that the reliance on self-reported data may introduce social desirability and response biases, potentially affecting the accuracy of the results.

The findings offer actionable insights for e-commerce managers seeking to optimize consumer engagement and purchase intentions. Given the strong influence of utilitarian motivations on online shopping satisfaction, managers may focus on enhancing functional aspects such as website usability, transaction efficiency, and product reliability. Integrating immersive and enjoyable shopping experiences—such as interactive content and personalized recommendations can further drive customer satisfaction and repeat purchases.

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